

Economic Recovery after a Financial Crisis

Part II (of IV)

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I -

Behavioural Motivation to Work

The need-drive-goal cycle represents a type of process approach to motivation. Cognitive dimensions are present in the goal in the motivation cycle. Cognitive elements have played a central role in certain theories of motivation.

The cognitive approach emphasizes our ability to make conscious, rational decisions and have perceptions concerning things like input/ output ratios and the value and probability of attaining future outcomes. Cognitive process theories recognize the complex nature of organizational behaviour.

Two of the most recently popular process theories with a cognitive perspective are the equity and expectancy theories of motivation.

Equity theory states that the motivation of a person to act is based on the comparison of his or her inputs/ outcomes ratio with the same ratio of a relevant other. In other words, there is an exchange relationship between the person and the other.

The perceived inputs into the ratio would include variables such as age, sex, education, social status, organizational position, and effort. Perceived outcomes in an organizational setting would be primarily rewards such as pay, status, and promotion.

If a person's perceived ratio is not equal to that of the other, then an inequity exists and the person will strive to restore the ratio to equity. When an individual is faced with an inequity, the person may alter the inputs or outcomes, distort the inputs or outcomes cognitively, leave the field, act on the other, or change the other.

Research to date on equity theory has had fairly positive results. One extensive review of the research literature concluded that:

- 1 The theory offers a relatively simple model to explain and to predict individual feelings about various organizational rewards.
- 2 The model should be relevant for organizational decision maker involved in determining appropriate levels of rewards.
- 3 The model can provide insights into the important area of reward interchange ability.

4 The theory can help identify individual or structural factors which evoke competing decision rules in organizations and the consequences of the rules.

The contributions equity theory could make to more effective human-resource management point out the value of studying the newer motivational approaches. The theory - practice gap can and must be bridged in the future to meet some of the critical human problems facing today's managers.

The **expectancy concept** is the probability that a particular effort will lead to a particular first-level outcome. It is different from instrumentality, which relates first- and second-level outcomes.

The expectancy approach as outlined above has developed into a sophisticated process theory of motivation. There is a fairly substantial amount of supporting research for the theory. Expectancy theory has been applied to field settings and seems to be making important advances in the prediction of satisfaction and organizational behaviour.

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Two points must be emphasized to clear up the misunderstanding surrounding these typical interpretations of motivated organizational behaviour.

- First of all, it should be recognized that people are motivated all of the time. The worker who is loafing or goofing off is exhibiting motivated behaviour.

- Secondly, and of more importance, is the fact that motivation can only be inferred from observable behaviours.

No one can actually see motivation. For example, one may observe a friend going into a local restaurant and conclude that he is motivated by hunger. In reality, he may be going into the restaurant for a rendezvous or to socialize with a group of buddies (his need to affiliate), or to be seen by the right people (for the sake of status), or for any number of reasons. The point is that motivation is an internal, unobservable explanation of behaviour.

Motivation should not be equated with the behaviour.

Motivation for Work

Most modern managers would recognize that motivation of their personnel is a critically important factor to successful human-resource management. Yet, despite this recognition, most managers know very little about human motivation and how it can

be more effectively channelled toward, instead of away from, organizational objectives.

One of the earliest attempts to explain motivation used the concept of instincts. According to this explanation, individuals had automatic, unlearned predispositions for certain patterns of behaviour. As the number of human instincts identified by researchers grew to nearly six thousand, it soon became evident that this was not an adequate explanation of human behaviour.

Many patterns were shown to be learned; and gradually researchers saw that although animals seemed to have predisposed patterns of behaviour (birds flying south in the winter or salmon swimming upstream to spawn), humans did not.

Today, very few behavioural scientists recognize instinct as the motive force behind human behaviour. Many do believe that there are certain unlearned primary drives (e.g., for food, water, and sex), but such drives are not predisposed patterns of behaviour.

Out of the dissatisfaction with the instinctual explanation of motivation evolved the drive theories. The term drive was used to represent the energizing influence that determined the intensity of behaviour.

Habit, on the other hand, reflected past learning and in particular the reinforcement concept this incentive factor was future oriented (as opposed to habit, which was past oriented). The incentive factor is anticipatory in nature.

The motivational cycle means that needs set up drives to accomplish goals. Needs are deprivations-either physiological (e.g., food, water, sex) or psychological (e.g., affiliation, achievement, power). Drives, on the other hand, are needs with direction.

Drives are the behavioural manifestation of needs. Goals are what the drives are aimed at. Goals will decrease the intensity of the drive and alleviate the needs.

A thirsty man can provide a simple example of the motivational cycle. The homeostatic balance of his body has been upset because his body cells have been deprived of water. This creates a motivational need. The man will attempt to restore the balance by setting up a drive-in this case, to search out a water fountain. The fountain is the goal. The thirsty man is much like the employee in an organization who has a need for achievement. The employee may set up a drive of working hard in order to achieve his goal, promotion into a responsible position.

Life in general and organizations in particular, do not always provide a smooth progression from needs to drives to goals. There are many barriers that prevent goal attainment. There are many stuck doors in life from the broken handle on the water

fountain that denies us a cool drink of water to bureaucratic rules and job designs that block opportunities for achievement and growth.

When motivated behaviour is blocked, the result is often frustration. Behavioural manifestations of frustration include: aggression (attempting to physically or symbolically injure or do harm to the barrier), withdrawal (backing away from the barrier and becoming apathetic, or in some cases regressing to an earlier state), fixation (pretending that the barrier does not exist) or compromise (choosing a more difficult path to the goal to circumvent the barrier or choosing an alternate but less desirable goal).

Much dysfunctional organizational behaviour can be attributed to frustration.

The worker who gets in fights hits his boss or sabotages the operation may be exhibiting aggression. The apathetic worker who daydreams and is a motivation problem may be experiencing withdrawal.

The employee, who keeps plugging away, knocking his head against the wall, may be doing so as the result of a fixation. The employee who quits or becomes a union organizer or lives outside the job may be experiencing compromise.

The challenge for the practitioner concerned with effective human-resource management is to remove some of the barriers that prevent employees from attaining goals. Of course, management must be careful to make sure that the goals of the motivational cycle of individual employees are compatible with the goals of the organization.

II -

Human Resources Formal Organization

Partly for moralistic reasons, but at least partly to forestall unionism, management began to modify its approach to administration. Beginning first with administrator own observations and later relying heavily on the results of the Hawthorne studies, the first large-scale social science experiments in industry, an emerging theory of administration began to treat employees as whole individuals who could not be broken down into component parts.

Thus, programs were developed to satisfy more than an individual physical and security needs, including, in addition, his need to feel important as an individual and to feel a part of his work group and the larger organization.

It is important to note that neither administrators nor scholars contributing to the development of this new administrative model tended to modify the widely held view that most organization members are incapable of self-direction and control.

Those who advocated increased efforts to keep employees informed, help them see how their jobs fit in, and involve people in decisions about how they are treated did so primarily with the goal of reducing resistance to organizational practices rather than with the intent of utilizing a broader range of capabilities of lower level members.

Thus, the Human Relations in that the task of administration was not perceived to be solely the creation of an impersonal, smoothly efficient organizational machine. However, viewed in retrospect, the Human Relations model did not represent an entirely new solution to the administrative problem.

Because of the utility of concepts such as rationality and stability, amply demonstrated by the traditionalists, administrators were naturally reluctant to give up many of the beliefs and techniques of the Traditional approach. Instead, the human relation tended to retain the structures and policies of the past and simply tried to make it less painful for employees to live with them.

Human relation hoped-in vain, as it turns out-those employees who were satisfied with their working conditions would respond by being highly productive.

The Human Resources model extended some of the basic tenets of each of the two previous administrative approaches. However, these extensions were also accompanied by some notable changes in the philosophy of administration.

Two of these changes were relatively straightforward. First, Human Resources theorists, applying the ideas of the late psychologist Abraham Maslow to the organizational arena, extended the list of human needs to which they felt administrators should be responsive from physical, security, and social needs to include self esteem and self actualization. Second, Human Resources theorists argued that many if not most organization members had far more capability for self direction and self control than their jobs demanded or allowed.

Moreover, these theorists argued that this full range of individual needs should be met, to the extent possible, by adapting organizational structure, job design, control systems, etc., to fit the preferences of individuals and work groups and to make greater use of their capabilities.

To argue that organization variables should give way to human variables, even for the purpose of improved organizational performance, represented a fundamental change in administrative thinking, and, as a consequence, the role of administration had to be reevaluated.

According to the description of the Human Resources the most recent conceptualization of the administrator role is not so much one of controlling organization members as one of facilitating their performance. However, lest we

convey the impression that the Human Resources approach argues for the breakdown of rationality, stability, and the other facets which the traditionalists saw so much need for, let us also point out that in the years since this model has become available, the understanding of alternative organizational forms and technologies has increased substantially.

Therefore, at the same time that the theory of administration has allowed for an increasingly expanded role for the individual, choices among organization variables have increased to the point where administrators can put together different blends of these two sets of variables rather than forcing one set to conform to the other.

III -

Employee's Role in an Organization

There is little argument that the selection of competent people is vital to the success of an organization. The argument comes when two or more people attempt to define the term competent.

From the organization planner's (that is, the concerned manager) point of view, the answer to the question of what constitutes competence may be found in the job definition itself.

Positions should be staffed with people who can and will do the job. Jobs should not be designed to fit the qualifications of a particular person. This view may cause no problems for the manager who is staffing an entirely new organization, but for the manager upgrading an existing organization it means trouble.

Consideration of the potential incumbent in the design of the job may contaminate many of the decisions that relate to job definition.

Staffing can be approached as a process. It involves analyzing job definitions to determine specifications against which potential job holders may be evaluated. This process can, and we think should, be used when analyzing the competence of an incumbent in any position.

A compilation of the skills, knowledge, experience, and traits that are required for a job can be summarized to form the specification against which candidates can be evaluated.

The types of staffing choices actually made will depend, as mentioned earlier, on whether a totally new organization is being staffed or an existing company is being reorganized.

When a manager finds, through an analysis of the incumbent staff, that personnel do not meet the specifications of their new jobs, few options are available: The incumbents either can be retrained to do the new jobs or other persons can be given the jobs.

The culture of the organization will control the reality of the situation. If the weakness of an incumbent is in only one or two new areas, it may be offset by the strengths in other areas of the job; or the areas of weakness may be covered by someone at the next lower level of the organization. If the manager is creating an entirely new position, he may be able to seek expertise from outside the organization, which is often easier than finding expertise in-house. However, the consequence of this action may be to diminish the motivation of those individuals who are relying on a promotion-from-within policy to get them to the top.

Managers very often must face the fact that the best persons they have within their organizations are not nearly good enough. A promotion-from-within program may in fact have created the situation, causing the organization not to develop the innovative climate needed to keep it constantly moving ahead.

Managers of companies with internal promotion policies also face the problem of having more than one adequate internal candidate for a job. This leads to the possibility that one might leave. Or a situation might arise in which the most likely candidate for the job is in fact too well qualified, and will undoubtedly become bored in a short time.

The **staffing process relies on a manager's skill at matching candidates with job specifications.** This requires use of effective interviewing techniques, proper screening, reference checking, and analysis of people chemistry.

Many managers maintain a score sheet to remind them of the success/failure rate of their staffing decisions. Most managers make better decisions when they use a rational process based on the needs of the job than when they use intuition.

Restructuring an organization has long-term implications. Those things discussed up till now-analyzing power, defining jobs, and developing good staffing techniques-are just as valid for long-term as for short-term planning.

In some organizations, long-term planning is a separate function concerned with scenarios for twenty-year periods. In others, long-term means next year or even next month. As used here, "long-term" refers to a three-to five-year planning period.

The process of designing an organization to meet five-year needs consists of:

(1) Determining objectives,

- (2) Determining benefits needed from the organization structure,
- (3) Designing the structure,
- (4) Allocating power,
- (5) Designing jobs for at least two levels of management, and
- (6) Determining specifications for each position.

At the end of this process the plan should know fairly well the ideal form projected for the organization five years in the future and be able to plan for change based on a comparison of present and future structure. From this comparison can flow any needed manpower development, personnel searches, or policies and procedures that will allow the organization to evolve into its proposed state.

IV -

Prediction and Control of Human Behaviour in Organizations

Respondent behaviour is reflex behaviour and is elicited by a prior stimulus. Respondent behaviour occurs when the environment acts on the organism in a stimulus-response fashion. For example: a doctor must tap (the environment) below a person knee in order for the leg to jerk out (respondent behaviour).

Operant behaviours are emitted by the organism and must be learned. Operant behaviour occurs when the organism acts on the environment to produce a consequence. The stimulus does not elicit a response but instead serves as a cue for the person to respond in a particular fashion.

The classical conditioning experiments of Pavlov and Watson helped to explain reflex or respondent behaviour.

The key to operant conditioning is what happens as a consequence of the behaviour. If the behaviour is followed by a positive or reinforcing consequence, the behaviour will be strengthened and subsequently increase in frequency. If the behaviour is followed by an unpleasant or noxious (punishing) consequence, the behaviour will weaken and subsequently decrease in frequency.

Thus, according to the theory of operant conditioning, the contingent environment takes on special significance. In this theory, antecedent cues and contingent consequences (both existing in the external environment) largely determine behaviour.

Viewed from the external perspective of organizational behaviour modification organizational behaviour is a result of its contingent consequences. Human-resource

management shifts away from managing people to managing the environment in which the people behave. This shift entails not only a new perspective but also a new way of managing people. It does not have to deal with complex internal causes of behavior but nevertheless effectively accomplishes the goals of understanding and, especially, prediction and control of human behaviour in organizations.

The three sequential steps in the model are outlined in the following paragraphs:

1. Identify.

1. The first step: **approach is to identify a performance-related behaviour problem.** This step deals only with observable, measurable behaviour. Attitudes, desires, motives, and other inner states are not treated. Moreover, only behaviours related to performance are targeted for change.

Many kinds of behaviour occur in any work situation, some related to performance and some not. For example, complaining is often identified as a behaviour problem, but it may have nothing to do with performance. Therefore, if the behaviour has nothing to do with performance, it is not appropriate for organizational behaviour model.

Conversely, a performance problem due to mechanical failure, lack of knowledge, or lack of training or ability is unsuitable for this technique. Only performance problems that are traced to behaviour are appropriate for Observation Models. Examples of such problems in an industrial setting would include productivity, quality, tardiness, absenteeism, and safety.

2. Measure.

After the performance-related behaviour problem has been identified, a baseline frequency must be obtained. A tailor-made tally is designed to measure how often the targeted behaviour is occurring under current conditions. This tally, which permits objective measurement, is then transferred to a graph.

The vertical axis represents frequency and the horizontal axis time. The resulting baseline is often quite revealing in and of itself. Sometimes the baseline indicates that the behaviour is occurring much more frequently than expected and sometimes much less frequently.

3. Intervene.

Intervention is the first action step of the organizational behaviour model approach. Based on the functional analysis undertaken in step three, an appropriate intervention strategy is developed. Positive reinforcement is without question the most effective strategy for accelerating desirable behaviour.

Natural as opposed to contrived reinforces should mainly be used. A natural reinforce is one already within the existing organizational setting. Social reinforces (attention, recognition, praise, and affection), feedback on job performance.

V -

The Traditional Model of Human Behaviour at Organizations

The Traditional model owes its existence to three major streams of thought relevant to administration. First, an important component of the Traditional approach is drawn from the writings of nineteenth-century philosophers and classical economists.

The philosophical doctrine prevalent at that time, Social Darwinism, argued that the fittest survive (and should survive), and that it was their duty to guide those of lesser ability.

Combine this belief with the classical economist's notion that leisure was man's preferred state and work his required state, and one has the makings of a theory that organizations were populated with a multitude of basically inept individuals who had to be forced to work through monetary incentives.

Extending this view and applying it to actual work organizations, Frederick Taylor and other members of the Scientific Management movement sought to improve productive efficiency by minimizing the constraints posed by untrained and unmotivated workers.

Taylor primary focus, documented in fact and in folklore, was task specialization. Armed with some newly developed methods (now referred to as time and motion study) and an unbounded zeal, Taylor and his contemporaries proceeded to make some very impressive strides in the improvement of work methods.

Working mostly at the shop-floor level, Taylor succeeded in numerous cases to improve both productivity and workers' wages through, essentially, separating the "planning" and "doing" of work.

Many of the concepts and techniques of the Scientific Management School have survived to this day and can be found in human-factors engineering, methods analysis, and work scheduling.

A third and highly influential set of ideas that helped to develop the Traditional model was provided by Max Weber, a German sociologist. Although writing at about the same time as Taylor, Weber focus was on the middle and upper reaches of organizations, not on the shop floor. However, though his vantage point was different, his message was frequently similar: Organizational processes were sorely lacking in rationality and efficiency. Actually, Weber concern was with the evils being foisted on

German society by the widespread nepotism and favouritism which existed in its public organizations, but his solution-bureaucracy-is today the dominant form by which the vast majority of organizations carry out their activities.

Bureaucracy is a system of interlinked offices (bureaus), each designed around a specific task and each containing a specific body of expertise, authority, and rules. Arranged hierarchically to facilitate coordination and control, these bureaus provide a stable structure in which the organization can perform its tasks relatively undisturbed by the movement of individual officeholders who might be promoted or who leave the system entirely.

Putting these major streams of thought together, three concepts central to the Traditional approach emerge: rationality, stability, and authority based on the office or position.

In the ideal Traditional system, the lack of employee expertise and motivation are mitigated by the careful design of jobs, a rational process of workflow through well-defined departments, and a deliberate separation of planning and direction from the actual performance of work.

Given the state of administrative knowledge and expertise prior to the development of the Traditional model, these were major improvements in the way organizations were administered.

VI -

Reorganizing the Organization

Existing structures seldom completely meet the anticipated needs of an organization. Most require some kind of ongoing modification if they are to be ready for new or expanded objectives and obstacles. Existing organizations reflect what the designers believed to be the needs of the enterprise at the time they were created.

Analysis of the benefits that should be provided by the structure may indicate that only slight modifications are needed. This of course allows for the creation of an ideal situation with a minimum of disruption.

One or two positions may be created or a position may be moved a level or two in the hierarchy to meet a need. The nucleus of a specialized group may be created so that it is in place and functioning prior to an anticipated expansion.

The manager who must totally redesign an organization structure usually must proceed at a faster pace than the manager who need only modify the structure. The following sections look first at some of the alternative types of structures available to

the manager, then present some advantages and disadvantages of each, and, finally, discuss some hazards to avoid when restructuring an organization.

Organizational structures are basically ways of dividing work. The critical question is which division is most effective. Six basic types are available, singly or in combination: function, product, customer, process, geography, and matrix.

Functional organization divides work into specific areas, each concentrating on one cluster of major objectives.

Different functional groups are prominent in different organizations depending on the objectives identified by the top manager. Each group concentrates on its own work, develops a high degree of efficiency, its own esprit-de-corps, and internal professional loyalty.

There is a tendency to look on other functional groups as adversaries, which may be counter-productive to achieving overall objectives. Functionally structured organizations require a great deal of well-thought-out coordination by the top manager.

One of the prime reasons for the failure of functionally organized enterprises to achieve their objectives is the lack of planned coordination at the top. Functional organizations usually provide opportunities for promotion at several levels for the personnel within the group.

The manager who must modify or redesign an existing structure should be aware of several design hazards as he tries to balance the optimum type of organization structure with the benefits needed.

The following sections identify the more common hazards. Although it may be necessary to incorporate one of these structural elements into a design, the manager should do it only with a complete awareness of the disadvantages that each poses.

Major design hazards include:

I. Creation of too many levels

a) Results in communication difficulties.

b) Is expensive.

c) Manager is far removed from the work, and organization is not responsive to directives

1. Difficult to get things done.

d) Authorities and responsibilities are too narrowly defined.

e) Managers find it difficult to get approvals. Decision making is slow.

Emphasis is placed on maintaining the status quo.

2. Duplication of Effort

- a) Results in wasted effort.
- b) Results in conflict between groups.
- c) Results in confusion as to where to take a problem.
- d) Authority relationship difficult to define.
- e) Primary responsibility cannot be pinned down.

3. Different Objectives in the Same Group

- a) Quality may be sacrificed for production.
- b) Top manager loses checks and balances.
- c) Production superintendent may not be able to balance conflicting objectives.
- d) The calibre of final inspection may be lower.

4. Reporting to More than One Boss

- a) Individual may receive conflicting orders. b) Individual has priority problems.
- c) Bosses may get into conflict over the individual.
- d) Raises the question of who has authority to hire, fire, give raises.

5. Improper Designation or Use of Assistants

- a) Role of assistant may be unclear and cause confusion.
- b) Title ("Assistant" or "Assistant to"?) can similarly cause confusion.
- c) Determination of level of assistant on staff may lead to dissension.

6. Moses Complex - (Too many people reporting to the same manager)

- a) Manager's efforts are spread too thin.
- b) One or more functions usually get neglected.
- c) Coordination becomes a major problem for manager. d) Manager may delay decisions.

7. One-Over-One - (Managers use assistant managers as buffers)

- a) Third-level managers must get through two levels to get action.
- b) Unless work is split neatly, there is constant duplication. c) Top manager has little impact on third-level management.

8. Loads Out of Balance

- a) One person is overworked.
- b) Some functions under one manager may be neglected.
- c) Only one manager has a chance to really understudy the plant manager.
- d) Functions of managers may be over emphasized in respect to other service functions.

9. Misplacement of Function (Placement of a general staff department under a specific line department-e.g., Industrial Relations under Production)

- a) Staff department will very likely serve only specific production department.
- b) Product manager supervises group which serves other functions; may get into conflict of interest.
- c) Staff department managers will be handicapped in relations with managers in other functions.
- d) Managers in other functions will most likely try to set up their own service groups.

10. Improper Organization Emphasis (Placement of a unit too low or too high in the organization structure-e.g., Engineering reporting to Plant Manager and Production reporting to Engineering)

- a) May result in illogical reporting or authority relationships-e.g., product subservient to Engineering.

b) Level of production groups will most likely mean lower salary levels hence, difficulty in attracting and keeping talent.

c) Relationships with other functions are hampered.

d) Plant Manager is remote from the critical

VI –

A -

Downsizing Work Force

Downsizing almost inevitably imposes substantial psychological costs on the workforce. It comes with some social costs for the community, at least in the short-term. And the available evidence on its bottom-line impact isn't clear. So the question "Must you downsize?" should be pondered carefully.

Of course, the costs and benefits of downsizing depend on the particular circumstances of the organization. If downsizing seemingly works best when tied to a plan for restructuring or repositioning, then the extent to which management has a good sense of what it is doing and why is crucial.

Family cultures, in which employment has been cast as a social bond rather than a stark exchange relation, are likely to suffer relatively more from downsizing.

Firms that depend on good relations with the surrounding community and that loom larger in the local labour market will also find downsizing to be more costly. Firms in a tight labour market will face a stronger adverse selection problem in terms of who departs, although a tight labor market will mitigate the damage to those who depart and thus on the community and on the psychological state of the survivors.

Technology and work organization also figure prominently. Where tasks are interdependent, downsizing tends to be more disruptive, both economically and socially.

Particularly when a firm's culture and technology emphasize cooperation across units, downsizing strategies that explicitly or implicitly pit different segments of the organization against one another in struggling to retain employees can be extremely destructive. One common solution to this problem is simply to mandate "across-the-board" layoffs, with each business unit being given a fixed percentage of headcount or payroll that must be trimmed.

With respect to business strategy, organizations that seek competitive advantage from continuous improvement or by transferring knowledge gained in one product, service, or division to another part of the firm will tend to suffer most from the knowledge losses wrought by downsizing.

If an organization has relied on secure employment, promotion from within, employee investments in firm specific training, and the like, layoffs can certainly be expected to undercut workers' confidence in the employer's representations about future prospects.

Organizations with seniority-based protections built into their human resources systems may stand to gain less economically from downsizing, because the layoffs will disproportionately hit workers with lower seniority, who are presumably making less money.

And obviously the cost implications of a layoff will depend substantially on the benefits plans an employer has adopted - for instance, its health and pension plans and obligations for continued coverage that may be mandated by law, collective bargaining agreements, or company policy.

In other words, in thinking through whether a layoff makes good business sense, an employer needs to be assessing both the impact of past human resources practices on the costs and benefits of a layoff, and the impact of a layoff today on the kinds of human resources practices the firm will be able to implement in the future.

Against these costs and the benefits to be accrued, you have to consider alternative actions the organization might take to address the problems or to meet the new circumstances that have led you to consider downsizing.

Wage cuts, hours adjustments, job transfers, and reassignment of work across plants are all alternatives to be considered. Especially when it comes to layoffs that respond to short-lived changes in economic conditions, such alternatives can be quite cost-effective.

Notice also in this regard that four important factors may bear on a firm's ability to avoid downsizing:

- a) Its inventory policy;
- b) The extent of uniformity in its operations (including human resources policies) across work sites;
- c) The extent to which it has cross-trained workers; and
- d) The extent of vertical integration.

One strategy taken by many high-commitment organizations to minimize layoffs is to respond to temporary downturns by producing for inventory or by redeploying workers to other tasks, such as deferred maintenance.

Another strategy sometimes used is to re-assign work across work sites, to smooth out fluctuations in demand.

This will be easier to do in a firm that is vertically integrated with a variable taper; then the taper can be adjusted, with workers deployed downstream when demand is strong and upstream when it is slack.

Of course, a firm's ability to re-assign work across sites will be easier to the extent that the firm has uniform operations and human resources policies in its different work sites. If a firm is running a high-commitment system in one site and a "high-control" system in another, it is harder to imagine how it could respond to a cyclical downturn by shifting work or workers from one of the sites to the other.

B –

The Effects of Downsizing Human Resources

A process issue that deserves careful thought in contemplating a downsizing concerns the choice between dramatic, swift cuts versus a more gradual, less wrenching approach. The advantages of a gradual approach are apparent: The firm may be unsure how deeply to cut and a onetime massacre runs the risk of cutting too much. Of course, the psychological costs may be attenuated by a gradual approach.

Local labour markets may be better able to absorb the discharged workers if they are discharged gradually, which in turn may ameliorate the adverse impact on the local economy and community.

On balance, however, those who have suffered through downsizing tend to believe that a "get it over with in one fell swoop" approach is superior (at least, for the firm) to a process that drags on.

A number of the beneficial effects such as increases in quality and productivity - do not manifest themselves for some time following the layoffs.

This suggests that a protracted process, in which it is presumably more difficult for employees to identify a discernible end to the layoffs and associated structural changes, may simply delay or prolong the adjustment period of up to a year or more that frequently seems to follow workforce reductions.

By moving boldly and rapidly, companies may minimize the long-term psychological damage and also perhaps achieve a more pronounced and rapid increase in shareholder equity.

When structuring a downsizing program, firms often must decide whether to implement cuts across the board, with every unit shedding a fixed percentage of its employees, or concentrate the cuts in specific units.

The costs of targeted layoffs are clear: They lead to internal political activity aimed at redirecting the decision at some other target. When our own university engaged in a large-scale "repositioning" some years back, which entailed the first significant layoffs in its long history, many of the staff support areas that had been targeted for the largest cuts spent enormous quantities of time in jurisdictional disputes and trying to document their workloads by creating forms, databases, and other devices intended to demonstrate to the university administration how much service they were providing.

Such political campaigning is apt to be particularly ferocious and disruptive when a firm's culture and technology emphasize cooperation and collegiality. In an attempt to head off such efforts, and also simply to avoid hard and painful decisions, management may - we believe, too often will - take the seemingly easy route of equally shared pain and across-the-board cuts in employment levels.

This route may seem easier for management, but it has real dangers for effective downsizing. For one thing, although a "share the pain" strategy of equal, across-the-board cuts may have some appeal as being distributive just, there can be significant perceptions of distributive injustice by units that are performing exceptionally or that have through disciplined efforts kept their headcount down and thus should be reduced less.

Management doesn't want to anger any of its workforces. De-motivating these units in particular is an especially bad outcome.

Across-the-board downsizing will also tend to score low on procedural justice because of the arbitrariness and inflexibility of the targets.

Appeal mechanisms that allow special pleading, which would increase perceptions of procedural justice, invite just the sort of politicking and internal competition that the across-the-board strategy is designed to pre-empt.

In addition, this sort of downsizing strategy, if it is anticipated in the future, may (perversely) lead unit-level managers to try to pad their payrolls, in anticipation of an across-the-board cut to come later.

For organizations with a strong clan - like culture - and especially if emotional bonds and task interdependencies are more intense within units than across units-this

"spread the pain" strategy will do just that: Everyone will feel intense loss of friends and colleagues, as opposed to having concentrated the pain in a few units. Finally, across-the-board downsizing have the same reactive odour as does downsizing alone (without some accompanying restructuring initiative): It signals to workers that management doesn't really have a well-thought-out plan for the future.

End of PART 2